

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

**Deliverable: D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the
H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles**

30/04/2020

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Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

This report summarizes NEANIAS activities and actions towards comprehensive Data Management which is aligned to EC guidelines and FAIR Data principles [1]. In particular, D1.5 describes NEANIAS data management plan and discusses the data management lifecycle to answer questions regarding both Ethical and Research data management.

NEANIAS cloud services will be able to support the data life cycle management of relatively large and heterogeneous datasets, will be based on best practices in coherence with the developments of the current and next generation EOSC frameworks. NEANIAS will secure openness and accessibility of the science results, data publishing in a useful manner and FAIR principles that are considered as baseline. By making NEANIAS data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable new ways of interdisciplinary collaborations will be enabled and complex and global challenges could be addressed through EOSC.

Deliverable 1.5 besides addressing which data, data types and data sources will be considered in the context of NEANIAS (Section 2) answers questions regarding the overall Research Data Management plan (Section 3), including:

- how can data be employed and exploited by NEANIAS services
- how long will datasets and products be kept
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/ made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

Further questions related to ethical data management are addressed in Section 4 includes:

- the employed privacy policies
- use and process of (end-) user data for research purposes
- ethical vs. compliance aspects of privacy
- any ethical implications of algorithms used
- lawful bases for data processing

1. Introduction

NEANIAS is an ambitious project promoting Open Science practices [2, 3] and playing an active role in the materialization of the EOSC ecosystem [4] by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities from three major scientific sectors: **Underwater** research, **Atmospheric** research, and **Space** research. Each sector will engage multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities, enabling the transition of the respective communities to EOSC concept and Open Science principles.

NEANIAS will develop, validate and integrate at EOSC **cutting-edge thematic** services which fill current gaps of operational service offerings related to the three research areas: *Underwater, Atmosphere and Space research*. Several signal processing, computer vision, machine learning, visualization core services, among others, will be developed along with user-specific innovative services tackling crucial and market-oriented tasks of their corresponding data life cycle. In particular, cross-cutting services will be developed which can be ultimately exploited and utilized by archeologists, geologists, renewable energy planners, robotic engineers, and others, from the academia, the industry and the public sector as well.

Abstracting on thematic service concepts and analyzing the opportunities of innovation on EOSC, NEANIAS will also deliver generic service offerings, i.e., core services (WP6) which will be reusable across thematic ones: *AI services*, that enclose also capacities for Machine Learning, *Visualisation services* that deliver state-of-the-art visualization as a service, *research lifecycle empowering services*, that provide essential tools for registering, locating, inspecting, sharing data and services and finally *EOSC/RIs Integration services* (WP7 and WP8) that allow the exploitation of EOSC and RIs offerings in a unified manner for NEANIAS services, including access to storage and computation and mechanisms for authentication and authorization.

NEANIAS will collect and utilize numerous datasets from a variety of domains such as earth observation, underwater optical and acoustic data, weather data and climate models, (radio)astronomy, and planetary observation missions. The different kinds of data which will be collected and managed in the platform include.

- **NEANIAS Research Datasets**, i.e., data collected, processed, generated, managed and stored for the purpose of the operation and delivery of NEANIAS services. Datasets will involve all thematic and core services, including data and accompanying metadata as they will be specified by each service. NEANIAS will deliver a service and data catalogue, a single-entry point for all services and research datasets managed within the projects;
- **Project Output**, i.e., any dataset collected during the requirement phase (via questionnaires and user interviews) and any datasets used for documenting and providing evidence for either a dissemination report or a publication produced in the context of project activities. These datasets are collections of standard material produced by research activities, e.g. deliverables, dissemination material, training material, scientific publications;

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- **Software-related data**, i.e., data resulting from the development and operation of the software enabling thematic and core services. These datasets are mainly software artefacts, logs and source code which can be used for various purposes including research tasks.

This deliverable is intended to be a **first version** of the NEANIAS Data Management Plan (DMP). NEANIAS participates to the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020, in line with the Commission's Open Access to research data policy for facilitating access, reuse and preservation of its research data. The DMP follows the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (version 3.0)¹. It contains an initial description of the datasets collected, processed or generated by the project and the plan on how FAIR data policies for making data findable, openly accessible, interoperable, and reusable will be applied.

The rest of the deliverable is organised as follows. Section 2 describes the main type of data managed by the project, i.e., the research data related to NEANIAS services and Section 3 outlines data management strategy including the FAIR data practices and facilities exploited for datasets storage (including Repositories), dissemination (including Catalogues) and preservation. Section 4 concerns ethical aspects and privacy policies for the use of the data and finally section 5 concludes the deliverable. In appendixes, detailed DMPs are presented as they have been collected and documented by service providers \ data owners via the use of ARGOS DMP software [5].

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

2. NEANIAS Data Types and Lifecycle

2.1. Data Description and Data Types

The thematic communities make use of a wide variety of datasets many of which will be considered within the scope of NEANIAS. Many of these datasets are external datasets which are already publicly available. At the same time, some of the data which will be used by NEANIAS' services have been or will be collected and curated by the members of the scientific communities involved in the project.

The details of the datasets which each thematic service consumes and produces are listed in the DMPs provided in the Annex of this deliverable as well as the respective deliverable of each thematic (i.e. D2.1, D3.1 and D4.1). In the following, the main data types considered by each thematic service are presented together with indicative data sources.

Underwater Services

U1 – Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data

The service considers acoustic multibeam data and produces bathymetric data of the corresponding regions. Datasets for developing, testing and validating the service will be considered, among others, from the following sources:

- MARUM (Germany) – e.g. Bahamas_MarineLandSlide, Kreta_MarineLandSlide, LakeConstance_ShipWreck ...
- NOAA (USA)
- BSH (Germany)
- IFREMER (France)
- NKUA (Greece) - e.g. Santorini

U2 – Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data

This service receives 2D image data with the corresponding navigation (orientation) information and produces a photomosaic of the area (map or image). Indicative sources for sample datasets include:

- IPGP-CNRS (France) – e.g. MOMAR 08, SUBSAINTES ...
- Universitat de Girona (Spain) – e.g. Cap de Vol, BOREAS ...
- AMU (France)

U3 – Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data

The seabed classification service considers multispectral multibeam data and produces classification maps of the relevant area. Among others, data made available from R2Sonic for the 2018 Multispectral Challenge will be used for developing, testing and validating the service:

- R2Sonic (USA) – Bedford Basin (2016, 2017, 2018), Patricia Bay (2016), NewBex (2016)

Atmospheric Services

A1 – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service

The GHG flux density monitoring service estimates energy fluxes (output data type) based on timeseries of atmospheric related measurements (input). Data collected from the Environmental and Networking Technologies and Applications (ENTA) unit of ATHENA will be considered as well as data from other sources:

- ENTA (Greece) – e.g. Athens Thermopolis, VOA-Gr station ...
- EUROPEAN FLUXES DATABASE CLUSTER (EU)
- AMERIFLUX (USA)

A2 – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions service

The service studies statistical results (correlation) and stress field maps given timeseries of atmospheric and earthquake related measurements. The main data sources considered for developing, testing and validating the service include the following:

- INGV (Italy) – e.g. Gas measurements, faults map and seismicity of Mt Etna (Italy)
- NASA (USA) – MODIS/MODVOLC thermal anomalies at selected volcanoes
- SI Global Volcanism Program - satellite measurements of SO₂ at selected volcanoes

A3 – Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service

The third atmospheric service produces geospatial maps of air quality forecasts (output) based on timeseries of in-situ and satellite atmospheric measurements (input). Relevant data sources that will be considered include:

- Porto Urban Data Platform (Portugal) – Porto Air Quality data
- IPMA (Portugal) – Meteorological data of selected regions
- OpenWeather (UK) – Meteorological data of selected regions
- MEE0 (Italy) – e.g. Sentinel-5P data

Space Services

S1 – FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata

The first space service considers images and datacubes from astronomical surveys and planetary missions for producing interactive geospatial/sky maps. Relevant data sources include, among others, NASA and ESA missions as the following:

- NASA (USA) – e.g. PDS, WISE, Spitzer ...
- ESA (EU) – e.g. Hipparcos catalogue, PSA, GAIA ...
- INAF-VLKB (Italy) - managing galactic plane astrophysical archives e.g. Hi-GAL, WISE, GLIMPSE etc.

S2 – Map making and mosaicking for multidimensional images

The map making and mosaicking for multidimensional images service takes multidimensional as input images and produces geospatial/sky maps. As in the case of S1, data from numerous

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NASA and ESA missions will be considered for developing, testing and validating the service, including:

- NASA (USA) – e.g. MRO, PDS, WISE ...
- ESA (EU) – e.g. PSA, Herschel...
- INAF-VLKB (Italy) - managing galactic plane astrophysical archives e.g. Hi-GAL, WISE, GLIMPSE etc.

S3 – Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques

The third space service specializes in the detection of relevant structures on datacubes from astronomical surveys and planetary missions (input) producing regions of interest where the structures are detected (output). As for the other space services, data from NASA and ESA missions will be used together with data from other sources such as:

- NASA (USA) – PDS, USGS
- ESA (EU) – PSA
- PLANMAP (EU)
- ATNF (Australia) – ASKAP EMU
- SKAO – SKA Data Challenge simulations data

The main data types consumed and produced by each service are summarized in the following table, together with the information of the contact person from NEANIAS project.

Table 1: Thematic services, raw and produced data types

Thematic Service	Raw Data Types (Consuming Data)	Produced Data Types (Products)	Contact Person
U1	Acoustic Multibeam	Bathymetric Map	Paul Wintersteller < pwintersteller@marum.de > Christian Ferreira < cferreira@marum.de >
U2	2D Image Data with Navigation	Photomosaic	Rafael Garcia < rafael.garcia@udg.edu > Nuno Gracias < nuno.gracias@gmail.com > Josep Quintana Plana < josepgp@gmail.com >
U3	Multispectral Multibeam	Classification Map	Konstantinos Karantzas < karank@central.ntua.gr > Makis Ntouskos < mdouskos@gmail.com >
A1	Timeseries of Atmospheric related measurements	Energy Fluxes	Spyridon Rapsomanikis < rapso@athenarc.gr > Fillipos Bodare < fillip_bd@hotmail.com >
A2	Timeseries of Atmospheric and Earthquake related measurements	Percentages of Correlation	Alessandro Tibaldi < alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it > Fabio Bonali < fabio.bonali@unimib.it >

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A3	Timeseries of in-site and satellite atmospheric measurements	Geospatial Map and Forecast	Ricardo Vitorino < rvitorino@ubiwhere.com > Francisco Cardoso < fcardoso@ubiwhere.com >
S1	Images/Datacubes from Astronomical Surveys and Planetary Missions	Interactive and Navigable Geospatial/Sky Maps	Eva Sciacca < eva.sciacca@inaf.it > Eugenio Schisano < eugenio.schisano@inaf.it >
S2	Multidimensional Images	Geospatial/Sky Maps	Angelo Pio Rossi < an.rossi@jacobs-university.de > Carlos Brandt < c.brandt@jacobs-university.de >
S3	Images/Datacubes from Astronomical Surveys and Planetary Missions	Detected Structures	Simone Riggi < simone.riggi@inaf.it > Filomena Bufano < filomena.bufano@inaf.it >

2.2. Source Code

Software has a special role in the Open Science landscape. Software is the carrier of intelligence and research-based knowledge in actionable form. Being one of the stops where data get manipulated, transformed or presented, it has a very important role in the process of new knowledge generation and as such access to it is essential for carrying out quite a few of the objectives of Open Science (repeatability, reproducibility, transparency).

Although Open Science is best served by open source code access, as it imposes the least restrictions on how to exploit the code and the research behind it, several paradigms and cases may be presented that do not substantially compromise its overall objectives.

NEANIAS follows an open, flexible approach with respect to software. Source code in NEANIAS is managed according to partner policies that dictate licensing, control, authoring, versioning and management. NEANIAS establishes the policies that assure quality of the delivered services. Initial information is captured in D7.1 “Delivery activities methodology and plan” and will be further detailed in D7.3 “Software Assessment Methodology”.

Although it is not a mandate of the project, the majority of code in NEANIAS is licensed under an OSS (Open Source Software) scheme. As such it may support a depositing policy that will allow researchers to inspect, replicate, reproduce and reuse both the code and the research behind it.

In general – assuming that respective license allows such a distribution - the source code of NEANIAS services will be deposited in Zenodo [6] as a minimal assembly of information [7] which consists of:

- A README file that contains at least the name of the software package, a short description, a reference to the project, software authors, other contributors, contact point(s), links to any active showcasing or servicing deployments and, if present, links to the code versioning system used for the code and binary releases.
- A LICENSE file that contains both the copyright and the licensing information of the source code.
- The source code itself.

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- If the source code contains 3rd party works that cannot be separated, then those should be contained along with their relevant licensing and copyright information.
- The code should be packaged in a compressed form, excluding binary elements (i.e. executables), deployment specific/configuration files, sensitive information, passwords, etc.

As it is the common practice in software code management, NEANIAS partners are already using solutions for code versioning and distribution. Those are not affected by the policy for Zenodo deposition of source code, which is selected for two main reasons:

- a. to empower the long-term preservation policy of source code independently of the sustainability and durability of the various source code management systems.
- b. to align the form of source code management planning independently of technologies and policies used by each partner, i.e. formatting, access rules, protocols, etc.

Regarding the **granularity** of software deposits those shall be defined by each service provider at a level high enough to enclose self-contained entities.

Regarding **timeline** of deposits, the suggestion is that those should take place at time intervals that the software is considered mature to conduct research via its use. At least one deposit at the end of the project is suggested for Open Source services. Coordinated deposits at milestones is the best option.

Summing up the Source Code Management Planning, it is expected that at key points in the service lifetime, copyright owners will (a) extract an instance of the source code from their respective code version control systems (b) compress the code in a common format (e.g. tar, tar.gz, zip), (c) author and package a few files of metadata (README, LICENSE) (d) upload the information package to Zenodo, along with code metadata and (e) obtain a DOI for the delivery of the package.

2.3. Reports and Publications

NEANIAS produces several types of presentation of its work. Those can be roughly summarized in the following:

- **Project report deliverables**, as described in its Description of Action. Those reports are of several confidentiality levels, yet most fall under the “Public” access class. As such they shall be published in open access repository and the EC project management platform, as supported by the relevant software. Confidential reports shall be only uploaded in EC project management platform [8] and protected appropriately by it.
- **Scientific Publications**, that may be produced by any scientific and/or technological research sector of the project. Complying with project funding mandate, all scientific publications will be published under Open Access principles, Green or Gold compliance depending on the case, yet targeting the project established KPIs in place.
- **Project dissemination artifacts**, which may consist of web and/or press articles, presentations, webcasts etc. This will be delivered under an Open Access license, most preferably CC-BY-4.0 [9]. Reasoned deviations may exist.
- **Training material**, which may consist of documents, presentations, webinars etc. Those will be delivered under an Open Access license. Owners are suggested to adopt one of Creative Commons 4.0 license, CC-BY-SA-4.0 [9] most preferable, yet reasoned deviations may exist.

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- **Technical documentation material**, which may consist of documents, wiki pages, diagrammatic descriptions etc. Those will be delivered under an Open Access license. Owners are suggested to adopt one of Creative Commons 4.0 license, CC-BY-SA-4.0 [9] most preferable, yet reasoned deviations may exist.

All those artifacts, independently of their licensing, will be registered in NEANIAS Research Products Catalogue (more details provided in D6.1) and harvested by OpenAIRE [10]. As such they will be accompanied by appropriate descriptions that follow the Dublin Core metadata schema, as a minimum requirement.

3. Data Management Strategy - Making NEANIAS Data FAIR

This section describes the Data Management Strategy applied to make NEANIAS data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) through detailing the internal policy and adopting Open Data guidelines [11] and platforms (such as Argos).

3.1. NEANIAS Internal Consortium Policy

NEANIAS Data Management policy is summarized in the following two elements:

- NEANIAS is participating in the Open Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020 and as such it adopts all relevant policies and guidelines.
- NEANIAS is pioneering by onboarding, as an early adopter, one of the first publicly available platforms to support actionable Data Management Planning, Argos, by OpenAIRE.

Regarding the 1st element of the policy, NEANIAS will not only comply with the Open Access publication policy and the provisioning of a Data Management Plan, but also adopts a robust path to support the FAIR research data principle, this deliverable being the first step in the direction. NEANIAS Data Management plan follows the guidelines of EC to promote data FAIRness in describing the life cycle of the data being gathered, processed and/or generated by the project by collecting information on:

- the handling of (research) data during and after the end of the project
- the particular data sets to be collected, processed and/or generated and their nature
- the methodology, technologies and standards that will be applied for data packaging, handling, description, sharing etc.
- the licensing / restrictions on data managed by the project
- the policies with respect to data curation and quality
- the policy with respect to data preservation (esp. beyond end of the project).

Regarding the 2nd element, Argos [5] is an open extensible service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance and of Data Management Plans. It is a service provided by OpenAIRE, entering its public access stage at the time of this deliverable authoring. Argos allows actors (researchers, managers, supervisors, etc.) to create actionable DMPs that may be freely exchanged among infrastructures for carrying out specific aspects of the Data management process in accordance with the intentions and commitment of Data owners. In order to facilitate the adoption of the platform, NEANIAS has engaged OpenAIRE experts since the beginning of the project to provide support on the use of the platform both in live presentations and as web training.

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Figure 1: Argos Data Management Platform

Argos is based on OpenDMP [12] which is by itself a free and open source software used for actionable machine Data Management Planning, that closely follows RDA DMP WG developments and specifications [13].

3.1.1. Data Management Responsible

NEANIAS does not hold a separate role for Data Management responsibilities. The responsibilities are shared by a few key individuals, the leading being the Innovation Manager, **Dr Katalin Kovacs (INNOMINE)**. Innovation Manager shall lead and coordinate activities that relate to data ownership and partner awareness.

Furthermore, three key project individuals will be responsible for providing data management planning for the three research sectors, in

- WP2 - Underwater research services, **Prof Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA)**
- WP3 - Atmospheric research services, **Prof Spyridon Rapsomanikis (ATHENA)**
- WP4 - Space research services, **Dr Eva Sciacca (INAF)**
- WP6 – Core services, **Dr Lovas Robert (SZTAKI)**

Data Management Planning related to business innovation cases will be addressed by the aforementioned Innovation Manager.

Regarding software, Data Management Planning will be led by the Technical Manager of the project, **Georgios Kakaletis (CITE)**.

Finally, data management planning related to research publications will be led by the Scientific Coordinator of the project, **Prof Konstantinos Karantzalos (ATHENA)**.

3.1.2. Data ownership and responsibilities

As a result of our effective Data and Innovation Management plan, the following will be created:

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- NEANIAS Inventory of Services: a database where all research results will be collected
- Individual innovation management and IPR strategy for each NEANIAS service

The following steps are applied for the project partners in order to create a database, as an inventory of services (details are in D1.4):

1. **Creating an inventory of research results:** Collecting and mapping research results and services and creating a so-called NEANIAS Inventory, where the research results with their main attributes are listed, which are all necessary information before starting any business development initiatives. The information collected and updated is required to be able to analyse the business opportunities behind each service.
2. **Identifying and analysing innovation opportunities:** The innovation manager and the WP leaders, preliminary analyse each service, based on the information collected and mapped in the NEANIAS Inventory. NEANIAS Inventory includes all the attributes to store the value, main elements of each service. As part of analysing each service, an individual innovation management and IPR strategy for each NEANIAS service will be investigated. This strategy includes the main steps in order to prepare for the exploitation of the service, and also include the potential business models and elaborate the main steps for IPR. The lessons learned during analysing the services will be shared with the WP leaders responsible for technology development.
3. **Data/Publication Access Policies and Licensing:** WP2, WP3 and WP4 leaders have to decide and list the core competences of each technology. After analysing the core competences, the innovation manager and the WP2-3-4 leaders, decide which of them should be:
 - a. Public: can be shared with the external stakeholders, and the users. Public information about the technologies does not hinder the added value of the product and does not jeopardize competitive advantage of the technology.
 - b. Protected by Non-disclosure Agreement (NDA): part of the core competence should be protected by NDA. This information is essential to share with external stakeholders, in order to foster collaboration and added value of the technology, however, it is an essential part of the competitive advantage, which should not be given away.
 - c. Protected by IPR: This should be negotiated with the project partners (WP2, WP3 and WP4 leaders) the innovation manager, and the Technical Board.

3.1.3. Intellectual Property

The general approach in NEANIAS regarding IPR handling is that

- (a) Any prior IPR is respected and maintained
- (b) IPR on project artifacts generated in the context of the project belong to the consortium members that participated in their generation

As clarified in the Consortium Agreement document, signed by all members of the consortium, the GA (General Assembly) is responsible for taking any decisions related to IPR (6.3.1.2 Decisions), while members can exercise veto in case they believe that their Intellectual Property Rights are threatened by project activities and/or decisions taken (6.2.4 Veto rights).

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Naturally any IPR on non-primary products of the project, such as derivatives, must respect any prior IPR that might reside inside or outside the project. Partners themselves are responsible for respecting IPR of any prior element, or extract they are utilizing in order to deliver their derivative datasets.

IPR management is a crucial part of NEANIAS and affects the handling of various elements: software, data, science/research knowledge, business and innovation cases. All background IPRs which remain in the ownership of the partner who is providing it. The foreground will be owned by those partners who generate it. Access rights to background and foreground will be granted royalty-free to other consortium members who need it for carrying out the project. Beyond the end of the project, the use of the tools developed during the project will be granted based on a royalty scheme.

“Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise commercially exploit the jointly owned results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:

(a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and

(b) Fair and Reasonable compensation.”

Consortium Agreement (Section 8.2, page 19) governed by Article 26.2 of the Grant Agreement

The process of developing the NEANIAS Inventory and developing individual innovation management and IPR strategy is strongly coordinated by the Innovation Manager, supported by the Innovation Management Team.

3.1.4. Long term preservation and Archiving

NEANIAS long-term preservation policy addresses both research artifacts and their metadata handled by its processes.

NEANIAS strategy with respect to long-term preservation and archiving builds on the following cornerstones:

- Data and their metadata shall be preserved in forms usable by services, at least for the contractual duration of the project. A five (5) years extended preservation is suggested as a best practice.
- Data and metadata repositories shall handle long term preservation and archiving on a best-effort manner, in which case they are required to offer transparency on the measures taken in the direction. In case an elevated, guaranteed service is offered, the terms of the service need to be presented.
- Data and metadata managers shall use open schemes (protocols/formats, etc.) that minimize the risk for long-term preservation braking changes to occur.

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- Security policy applied by each system in place must be sufficient to support at least the most restrictive form of data access required to secure the data and metadata deposited.
- Data managers are responsible for clearance of rights and application of those in the underlying preservation system, as well as for ensuring that the protection features cover the minimum requirements posed by data copyright owners.
- In case additional/redundant depositing/cataloguing services exist that can enhance the options of data/metadata to survive long time frames, use is encouraged by the project, as long as those comply with the data protection rules settled by the data owner/manager.

Moreover, the long preservation and archiving of research data resources involved and further developed within NEANIAS services (such as the ones in S1 or C4) will continue to be maintained as part of each NEANIAS partner/institution data center. Besides that, upgrades can happen on request by future projects, like it is happening currently with the ERC Synergy Grant ECOGAL [15] and eventual future projects that will support maintenance and updates to the VLKB [16] for research on star formation regions and galactic plane research.

External data sources employed by NEANIAS services will be taken care by the respective data centers and many of them, such as GAIA [17], are already mirrored in other data centers worldwide.

3.1.5. Data security

Acting in the area of Open Science and data FAIRness, it is often misunderstood that data security is of lesser importance than in other cases, however this is far from being true. Not only data security is an essential aspect of Data Management Planning, but it also poses additional challenges due to the breadth and mix of policies that may be present in a discipline. In the general case, this creates a vast landscape of options that needs to be nailed down to the specific requirements in order to be strategically and technologically addressed in the context of a project, such as NEANIAS, that operates within a focused plan and a limited timescale.

Thus, starting from (a) requirements posed by thematic sectors, (b) need and relevance of data security in general and (c) technology relevance in the project, in the following we present the cornerstones of data security policy in NEANIAS.

Data confidentiality

Data confidentiality addresses both data and metadata, yet policies differ substantially among those.

NEANIAS strongly suggests **open publication of metadata** of data that may be reused in any foreseeable case inside and outside the project, independently of the access type granted to data. Yet temporal or internal reference data may well deviate from the rule. Those metadata need to be registered at least in internal project's research product catalogue and, depending on policies, may be openly accessible to 3rd parties.

In addition to delivery of metadata, it is essential that a declarative, comprehensible license is provided. If targeting open access under restrictions, the choice of one of CC 4.0 flavors [9] is suggested, however data owners are free to select any existing or provide a new licensing

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

scheme that covers their needs. It is evident though that along with the license a clear statement of ownership of the data is required. Actionable licensing is most preferable, however there are little chances that this is enforceable by several systems in place.

Regarding data, although NEANIAS suggests an **open access data** delivery as the baseline policy, however as most data handled are results of prior work or are derivatives of data with restrictive licenses this will be applied at data owner's discretion. Thus, a data owner may opt for private, restricted or open access (with or without limitations) of data. In case data are kept private, those may not be accessed by any other users inside or outside NEANIAS ecosystem. Restricted use may have different meanings depending on the service in question, thus data owners shall be aligned to service activities for granting data access to those services. For instance, "restricted use" may imply that the service grants access to underlying raw data according to an access policy, or that may base its processing to deliver open access data using the original data, which are two cases substantially different. Open access on the other hand, can be provided also under restrictions, as for instance a requirement for user registration or limited use of data etc.

Another aspect of data protection option is the establishment of an embargo period on fresh data, in order to protect the interests of the owner, yet not substantially impact their reuse by other scientist. Common practices of 6- or 12-months embargo (even 24 in several cases) are usually employed in the Open Access world.

Data dependability

Another aspect that data security policy in NEANIAS refers to data trustworthiness. This is addressed with policies in several directions.

- Data integrity needs to be safeguarded both for data and metadata by storage service and catalogues and, if possible, further augmented by author seals.
- Authorship shall be well registered and tacked so that repudiation or any other relevant false claims are prevented.
- Versioning of data / metadata is ensured so that consumers may precisely address the artifact in question.
- Metadata description is adequate to support introspection of data and accurate consumption of the latter.
- Provenance is tracked adequately to support comprehension of data origins, generation procedures and ownership respect.
- Strong referencing of data is provided so that any further claims may be routed appropriately.
- Long term preservation is enabled allowing data to be dependable in the future.

Technology-wise, secure storage of the data will rely on the cloud services architecture provided by WP6 and WP7 employed to store the data. Those services, present either inside or outside NEANIAS infrastructure, will provide the functionality and guarantees needed to address secure storage and data security.

3.2. Making NEANIAS data FAIR

According to the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020² this section of the Data Management Plan is expected to give answers to the following questions:

- ✓ Is the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?
- ✓ Will be provided possibilities for re-use?
- ✓ Do you provide clear version numbers?
- ✓ What metadata will be created?
- ✓ In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Based on the above guidelines and on the directions presented on the NEANIAS Deliverable 6.1 “Core services architecture, design principles and specifications report – Implementation Plan” [18], the FAIR Data Management policy will be accomplished by the following principles and Implementation Plan:

Findable data. Access to the service catalogue and service metadata will be provided through the NEANIAS service catalogue portal. The NEANIAS portal will offer browsing and keyword search functionality to enable users to discover and find services in an intuitive manner. The service catalogue and each service entity will be described by a clear set of metadata (schema), the Service Description Template (SDT) provided by the EOSC Portal onboarding team, and more specifically the EOSC Enhance project [19] which is responsible for operating and implementing the current phase of EOSC portal. The data catalogue will be provided through OpenAIRE’s Zenodo platform [6]. Zenodo’s metadata is compliant with DataCite’s Metadata Schema [20] minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo’s search engine. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there. Both the service and data catalogues will support versioning. A globally unique and persistent ID (PID) will be assigned to every resource via Zenodo.

Accessible data. The NEANIAS portal will provide continuous access to the service and data catalogues via the web. The NEANIAS service catalogue will also provide continuous access to the catalogue via standard APIs that are HTTP REST APIs. The description of the Service Model is documented in the API documentation page and is available for download in JSON formats [21]. The data catalogue will be provided through OpenAIRE’s Zenodo platform. All metadata in Zenodo for individual records as well as record collections is harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol [22] by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. Data and metadata in Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

Interoperable data. Each service collected in the NEANIAS service catalogue will be stored in the Service Data Model as a separate XML/JSON file. For metadata interoperability, service schema will reuse terms from widely known vocabularies and ontologies such as the Dublin Core [23] terms and SKOS [24], including taxonomies and classifications for enumerated attributes of a service. Similarly, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. Interoperability will be supported by the provision of dedicated APIs that allow the import and export of the content in standard formats (XML, JSON) and standard data models.

Re-usable data. The public content within the NEANIAS catalogue and services will be available for download and re-use with no restrictions or embargo. The content will be available under permissive licenses, (CC-BY 4.0, CC-0 or comparable) but certain conditions (e.g. Noncommercial use=NC) and/or exceptions may also apply. The NEANIAS service catalogue will be built based on the eInfraCentral [21] software which is available under the GPL/A license. In the cases where specific service information cannot be publicly shared, the reasons will be mentioned in their metadata descriptions (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related). In Zenodo, the code is open source, and built on the foundation of the Invenio digital library [25] which is also open source. The work-in-progress, open issues, and roadmap are shared openly in GitHub. All meta data is openly available under CC0 license, and all open content is openly accessible through open APIs. License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an Open Definition license [26]. Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.

Thematic Services

As far as the management of the data manipulated by each thematic service or community is concerned, the following table summarizes the main aspects of the respective DMPs (see Appendix). Specifically, aspects relevant to making data FAIR are highlighted and compared among the different services/communities.

Table 2: Aspects of the individual data management plans of the thematic NEANIAS services

		Underwater			Atmospheric			Space	
		U1	U2	U3	A1	A2	A3	Astrophysics	Planetary
General	External data	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Searchable Metadata	Yes	Yes (when relevant)	Yes (when relevant)	Yes	Yes (when relevant)	Yes (when relevant)	Yes	Yes
	Versioning	Not required	Not required	Not required	Not required	Not required	No	Yes	Yes
	PID	DOI	DOI	DOI	DOI	DOI	PUI	Yes (IVOA)	TBD

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Accessibility	Open Formats	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Ethical/Legal issues	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
	Open accessibility	For some	For some	For some	For some	Yes	Yes	For some	Yes
Inter-operability	Repository/Service	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	TBD	Quantum Leap	ViaLactea KB	Custom service
	Standard vocabulary	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	For some	Yes
	Licensing	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Reusability	Quality Assurance	Yes (project end)	Yes (project-wise)	Yes (project-wise)	Yes (project-wise)				
	Duration	As by contract	As by contract	5 years	As by contract	As by contract	5 years	5 years	5 years
Security	Data of limited use	Secure database	Secure database	Kept secure	Secure database	Secure database	Kept secure	Kept secure	Authent. / Authoriz.

	<i>Common Management Plans</i>
	<i>NOT Common Plans</i>

It is noted that all thematic services agree on the need to use external data for their operation/validation, the intent to produce searchable metadata and the use of open data formats. Additionally, all services agree on providing quality assurance as it will be defined within the context of the NEANIAS project. Finally, all thematic services assume no ethical or legal issues concerning the data and plan to provide details regarding data licensing at a later stage.

At the same time, there are different considerations among the services regarding other aspects of the respective data management. For example, many services plan to use DOIs as persistent identifiers while other prefer other identifiers used within the specific community (e.g. Astrophysics). Also, only some of the services foresee the need to adopt a versioning scheme for the data. Regarding the repositories or the services through which the data will be made available, many services plan to use Zenodo while some of the Atmospheric and Space communities plan to use dedicated services employed by their communities. The duration for which reusability of data is supported also varies. Finally, regarding the accessibility of the relevant data, some of the services plan to make all data available to the public while others plan to keep some of the data restricted by employing different solutions for keeping the data secure.

4. Ethical Aspects and Privacy Policy

4.1. Privacy Policy and EU General Data Protection Regulation

According to the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, this section of a Data Management Plan is expected to give answers to the following questions:

- ✓ Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?
- ✓ Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Privacy and Data Protection become relevant in the context of NEANIAS where the data processed as part of the project analysis constitutes personal data as defined by the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) i.e. any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject), whereby “an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”

Research in NEANIAS but not only is clearly not the preserve of academia. The interface, including the exchange of data, between research organisations and the wider research ecosystem are highly complex. Scientific publishers, developers, entrepreneurs, commercial, governmental and non-profit funding sources in the commercial, governmental and non-profit sectors, all potentially have a stake. In NEANIAS, we share the same opinion and act accordingly with the European Data Protection Supervisor³ and argue that the processing of personal data for the purposes of ‘academic expression’ implies: (i) processing directly linked to the freedom of academics to disseminate information, (ii) their freedom to distribute knowledge and truth without restriction, such as with publications, dissemination of research results, and (iii) the sharing of data and methodologies with peers and exchanges of views and opinions.

Concerning the ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing in NEANIAS, based on the Datasets table presented above, no ethical or legal issues foreseen for any of the generated dataset.

With regards to second basic question if it is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, NEANIAS is requesting compliance for collection and reuse of data. A dedicated work has been taken place already within the 6 first months of the project concerning a full privacy policy for the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR). Describes the policies and procedures in place by NEANIAS to protect the privacy of users, how the confidentiality of such information is ensured, laws, rights of data subjects and a communication path for further clarifications.

³ European Data Protection Supervisor, 2020. Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research

4.2. Lawful bases for data processing, including cases that NEANIAS users are children

NEANIAS cloud-services users actively use NEANIAS products/offerings, which makes it possible to obtain their consent or justify the processing of their data by means of the contract into which they have entered in order to use the relevant services.

Where the users are children, one will have to take into consideration Article 8 of the GDPR. Whereas NEANIAS services/products will be offered as cloud services (i.e. online interactive service) directly to a child, typically a student, the processing of the personal data of the child shall be lawful where the child is at least 16 years old. Where the child is below the age of 16 years, such processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that consent is given or authorised by the holder of parental responsibility over the child. The controller must make reasonable efforts to verify in such cases that consent is given or authorised by the holder of parental responsibility over the child, taking into consideration available technology. We note that Member States may provide by law for a lower age for those purposes.

4.3. Ethical and compliance implications of Machine Learning algorithms

In NEANIAS we have considered ways to tackle the risks associated with the development and service provision of AI-based solutions both during development and operation phases. In particular, NEANIAS will follow the set of EC non-binding Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI⁴ i.e., implement 'human-centric' approach to AI that is respectful of European values and principles: *“The human-centric approach to AI strives to ensure that human values are central to the way in which AI systems are developed, deployed, used and monitored, by ensuring respect for fundamental rights, including those set out in the Treaties of the European Union and Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, all of which are united by reference to a common foundation rooted in respect for human dignity, in which the human being enjoys a unique and inalienable moral status. This also entails consideration of the natural environment and of other living beings that are part of the human ecosystem, as well as a sustainable approach enabling the flourishing of future generations to come.”*

NEANIAS core and thematic services will consider all critical factors⁵ of human agency and oversight, robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, societal and environmental well-being, accountability.

Therefore, transparency in NEANIAS is of paramount importance in order to ensuring that AI is not biased and AI systems been deployed are explainable.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

⁵ Tambiama Madiega, 2019. EU guidelines on ethics in artificial intelligence: Context and implementation, EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

4.4. Data controllers and processors

NEANIAS consortium members are expected to be in the role of the data controllers with regard to the data gathered from the Service activities. However, subject to future commercial arrangements for the backend technologies exploitation, it may be possible for consortium members to act as data processors for their clients. In such cases, the responsibilities towards data subjects would primarily fall on the clients. However, under Article 28 of the GDPR [27], NEANIAS consortium members would still need to assist the clients in fulfilling their obligations under GDPR towards data subjects whose data would be processed by the system.

References

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- [13] OpenDMP [<https://gitlab.eudat.eu/dmp/OpenAIRE-EUDAT-DMP-service-pilot/>]
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D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

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- [24] SKOS Schema [<https://www.w3.org/TR/2008/WD-skos-reference-20080829/skos.html>]
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- [26] Open Definition license [<https://opendefinition.org/>]
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APPENDIX – INDIVIDUAL DATA MANagements PLANS

NEANIAS WP2 U1 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Sample datasets, collected during research cruises, are made available to test and demonstrate the applicability of the proposed service. Of course, this is part of the project objectives along with the availability of large data sets.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The service will generate digital terrain models as raster data (so called grids) in the NetCDF GMT format, ESRI ASCII grid format or simple ASCII XYZ as well as PDF/PostScript.

The sample datasets itself are recorded in a vendor proprietary but openly described binary format.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Existing data will be used for service validation purposes.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Survey data come from research or test cruises, vessel-mounted devices and some/one from AUV mounted device.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

Several GBs per acquisition.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers and stakeholders with activities in underwater marine environments.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Comment: Datasets come with a predefined naming

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

No

Comment: Not required

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

www.PANGAEA.de

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

Raster/gridded data: NetCDF GMT; ESRI ASCII Grid, ASCII XYZ. Calibration info and Navigation file: ASCII, CSV format

2.1.17 Standardised formats

As above

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

For all data

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

some

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

bathymetry and backscatter binary vendor files and navigation files, sound velocity profiles

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Zenodo? Would be good to discuss this topic asap.

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

The raw sample data: Yes – It's purpose of the service

The service products can be opened in Open GIS or other tools.

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?
processed binary datasets for further investigations incl. log of the workflow, publication

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

all

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

The sample data (if not confidential once) will be accessible within this year via www.Pangaea.de

2.4.4 What internationally recognised license will you use for your data?

Do not know yet

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes, but improvements or not will be available at the end of the project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

As long as it is stated and required by the project contract.

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

For the given sample datasets: DGF / German Government through www.pangaea.de

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

NEANIAS Data Manager, www.pangaea.de

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional / companies archive

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

Kept on secure database/storage.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP2 U2 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

- Data Repositories
- External Datasets
- Registries
- Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Experimental data, collected in the field, are made available to test and demonstrate the applicability of the proposed service. Of course, this is part of the project objectives along with the availability of large data sets.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The service will generate GeoTIFF images, in the case of 2D mosaics, and 3D triangle meshes in Wavefront's OBJ format, in the case of 3D reconstructions.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Existing data will be used for service validation purposes.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Surveys came from AUV, ROV and diver image acquisitions.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

Several GBs per acquisition.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers and stakeholders with activities in underwater marine environments.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes, vocabulary to be selected

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Comment: Datasets come with a predefined naming

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Comment: Not required

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

At least Zenodo keyword search would be provided

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

IMAGES: GeoTIFF , JPEG, PNG. Calibration info and Navigation file: ASCII, CSV format, JSON

2.1.17 Standardised formats

As above

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

For all data

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

some

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

Underwater images, camera calibration files and navigation files

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Zenodo or local storage at Coronis private server

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery (depends on Zenodo)

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

Publication related to the dataset

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

all

2.4 Increase data reuse

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

same as publication

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

Do not know yet

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes, but improvements or not will be available at the end of the project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

As long as it is stated and required by the project contract.

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Only through NEANIAS

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes, NEANIAS Data Manager

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

Kept on secure database.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP2 U3 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

- Data Repositories
- External Datasets
- Registries
- Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The consumed multispectral multibeam data are multidimensional images and come in a geotiff file format.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Existing data will be used for service validation purposes

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

The are acquired from multispectral multibeam surveys

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

Several GBs per acquitition

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers and stakeholders with activities in underwater marine environments

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Comment: We will use the suggested from OGC for geospatial mapping products

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Comment: Datasets come with a predifiend naming

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Comment: Not required

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

Comment: yes

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

Other

Comment: GeoTIFF

2.1.17 Standardised formats

<http://geotiff.maptools.org/spec/geotiffhome.html>

GeoTIFF

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

foralldata

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

some

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

Multispectral multibeam

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Zenodo

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

securewithbackupandrecovery

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

publication

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

all

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

after

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes

Comment: At the end of the project

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

uptofiveyears

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

other

Comment: through NEANIAS

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment: NEANIAS Data Manager

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

institutionalarchive

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

keptonsecure

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP3 A1 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

- Data Repositories
- External Datasets
- Registries
- Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Experimental data, collected in the field, are made available to test and demonstrate the applicability of the proposed service of our algorithms (models) use. Of course, this is part of the project objectives along with the availability of large data sets.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The experimental data will be (and are) available in the format that the models will use. As inputs to these models they are available in time marked ASCII format (CS-Variables of x columns and y rows)

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Existing field data will be used for service validation purposes

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

The are acquired mainly from Meteorological towers and from aircraft campigns

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

Several GBs per acquisition, preferably reduced by converting to ASCII.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers, stakeholders and meteorological and other authorities with activities in town planning (energy fluxes), greenhouse gases inventories, agriculture(transpiration) etc...

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes, as suggested by WMO and the GEO project of the UN.

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Comment: Datasets come with a predifiend naming

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Comment: Not required

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

URL addresses of data repositories

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

ASCII, CSV format

2.1.17 Standardised formats

As above

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

For all data

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No, Users will be asked to confirm quality of data by “round robin exercises”

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

some

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

Meteorological data applicable to the field of “Micrometeorology”

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Zenodo

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

Yes, in peer reviewed international publications

2.3 Making data interoperable

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

Yes, assuming that the user understands it.

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

After their validation by the users and after the end of the project.

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

Do not know yet

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes, but improvements or not will be available at the end of the project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Of course.

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

As long as it is stated and required by the project contract.

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Only through NEANIAS

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes, NEANIAS Data Manager

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

Kept on secure database.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP3 A2 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The H2020 NEANIAS Project aims to design, deliver, and integrate into the European Open Science Cloud innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In the framework of WP3, NEANIAS will deliver cloud-based services that target specific challenges of the atmospheric thematic sector. Within this service, the A2 activity will focus on monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions. Experimental data regarding radon emissions and earthquake parameters, collected in the field and obtained from pre-existing datasets, are made available to test and demonstrate the applicability of the proposed service; this is part of the project objectives along with the availability of large data sets.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The experimental data consist in dataset of radon emission measurements, atmospheric conditions (pressure and temperature), and earthquake parameters (magnitude, geographic coordinated and depth of the hypocenter). Data will be (and are) available in the CSV format.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Existing field and seismological data will be used for service validation purposes.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Radon emission measurements and atmospheric parameters have been collected by a radon probe situated on Mt. Etna. Earthquakes parameters are taken from the INGV-OE seismic catalog.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

~ 6 MB

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers, stakeholders and other institutions working in the field of hazard and risk mitigation (e.g. civil protection)

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

CSV format

2.1.17 Standardised formats

As above

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

For earthquake data

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

Yes

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

All data

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Do not know yet

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

Yes

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

After their validation by the users and after the end of the project.

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

Do not know yet

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

As long as it is stated and required by the project contract.

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Only through NEANIAS

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes, NEANIAS Data Manager

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

Kept on secure database.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP3 A3 Service – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020 External References

Data Repositories External Datasets Registries Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The H2020 NEANIAS Project aims to design, deliver, and integrate into the European Open Science Cloud innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In the framework of WP3, NEANIAS will deliver cloud-based services that target specific challenges of the atmospheric thematic sector. Within this sector, the activity 3 will focus on the air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service implementation. The data will be used to feed and validate the developed modules based on the considered weather forecasting modules.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Consist of a set of measures regarding Air Quality since 01/12/2018. The measured parameters are: CO, NO₂, O₃, O_x, PM₁, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. This data is provided using FIWARE data models.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes, it will be used existing data from another project that is publicly available from city of Porto. The data will be used to feed and validate the developed modules based on the considered weather forecasting modules.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

They are collected from physical stations spread over the city of Porto.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

~150MB.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Several researchers and stakeholders with activities in atmospheric services.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

other

Comment: Fiware data models

(<https://fiware-datamodels.readthedocs.io/en/latest/Environment/AirQualityObserved/doc/spec/index.html>)

2.1.2 URL/Location

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

not listed

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

Comment: We will use FIWARE data models standard

2.1.4 URL/Description

<https://fiware-datamodels.readthedocs.io/en/latest/Environment/AirQualityObserved/doc/spec/index.html>

2.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

2.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

2.1.8 URL/Name

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: Each air quality station is identifiable

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

Persistent Unique Identifier

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

Comment: Fiware data models

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

Other

2.1.17 Standardised formats

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

Comment: JSON

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

all

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Not Listed

Comment: The data will be available through QuantumLeap (public service that provides the data)

2.2.6 URL/Name

<http://history-data.urbanplatform.portodigital.pt/>

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

securewithnobackupandrecovery

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

auxiliary

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

all

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

end

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

your data?

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of

Yes

Comment: We will follow quality assurance procedures of the NEANIAS project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?
useofinstitutioninfrastructure

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment: The NEANIAS WP4 Astrophysics Data Manager is Ricardo Vitorino

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

Kept on secure

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP4 SPACE - Planetary Services – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020 External References

Data Repositories External Datasets Registries Services

Dataset Description

Many of the data archives sourcing the data our services will use work as PDS services – Planetary Data System is a model for data storage and distribution. All PDS archives listed below follow the third version of the protocol, PDS3. Section PDS provides a general description of a PDS archive.

Data Repositories

To be defined.

External Datasets

- MEX HRSC Reduced Data Records (REFDR)

[ohhttps://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mex/mex-m-hrsc-5-refdr-dtm-v1/mexhrs_2001](https://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mex/mex-m-hrsc-5-refdr-dtm-v1/mexhrs_2001)

- MRO CRISM Targeted Reduced Data Records (TRDR)

[ohhttps://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mro/mro-m-cris-3-rdr-targeted-v1](https://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mro/mro-m-cris-3-rdr-targeted-v1)

- MRO HiRISE

[ohhttps://hirise-pds.lpl.arizona.edu/PDS/](https://hirise-pds.lpl.arizona.edu/PDS/)

- MRO CTX (EDR)

[ohhttps://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/data/mro/ctx/](https://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/data/mro/ctx/)

- MGS MOLA

[offtp://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mgs/mgs-m-mola-5-megdr-l3-v1/mgsl_300x/](ftp://pds-geosciences.wustl.edu/mgs/mgs-m-mola-5-megdr-l3-v1/mgsl_300x/)

- LRO LROC

[ohhttp://wms.lroc.asu.edu/lroc/rdr_product_select](http://wms.lroc.asu.edu/lroc/rdr_product_select)

- PLANMAP geological maps

[ohhttps://data.planmap.eu/pub](https://data.planmap.eu/pub)

- Mars Global Digital Dune Database MC-1

[ohhttps://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2010/1170/](https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2010/1170/)

- Mars Global Digital Dune Database: MC2–MC29

[ohhttps://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2007/1158/](https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2007/1158/)

- Mars Global Digital Dune Database: MC-30

[ohhttps://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2012/1259/](https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2012/1259/)

PDS data archives

Planetary Data System (PDS) is an assemble of (i) data archive (structure) standards and (ii) data access thematic nodes. The former, standards, state the rules through each missions and data providers should lay down datasets content. Current version of PDS standard is 4 -- PDS4 --, though most of the imagery archives of our interest follow the version 3 (PDS3).

The thematic data access nodes split planetary data according to their scientific subject, for instance, we -- as geoscientists -- relate to the PDS Geoscience Node (PDS-Geo).

Registries

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

IVOA Registry-of-Registries and OGC Catalogue services.

Services

OGC Services and FTP for direct data access.

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The Planetary group of NEANIAS will provide imagery analysis tools of highly demanded planetary bodies -- Mars and the Moon. For simplicity, hereafter called bodies. The goal is to scale up services we have developed during recent years to a larger audience, comprising scientists, engineers, educators and their students.

To provide the services for image mosaicking, map macking, landing sites evaluation, or analysis on the composition of the surface we will handle data sets composed by images, and their metadata, mainly, as well as vector databases.

Planetary images from different wavelength, resolutions and observation angles provide complementary information to each other to create higher-level products. We will use data already reduced -- photometrically, spatially calibrated images --, from different wavelengths or digital terrain models. Vector data sets are used to annotate images, either as regions or specific locations.

Geolocation is the primary feature of our data. Database systems capable of managing geolocated data -- either images or tables -- are responsible to handle their storage as well as access.

In the following sections, we provide the list of data sets to be handled, followed by their description, and the interface to users and internal system components. As the project evolves, the content of this document will evolve accordingly as to accommodate the details of our data software system.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Our services will handle at some point a composition of raster and vector data to provide surface imaging featured by attributes either by the projects data processing tasks or merged from source data archives.

Raster data groups typical images -- i.e., bi-dimensional data arrays -- as well as data-cubes -- multi-dimensional images, the third-dimension is filled by fine-resolved spectra or discrete spectral indexes. Vector data are asymmetric multi-dimensional tabular data, typically encoded in text format where one or more columns provide geometric features like polygons, lines, or points.

Specifically:

- GeoTIFF
- GeoPackage
- PDS IMAGE/CUBE
- PDS LABEL

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Most of the data came from public repositories, some of them will be released to the NEANIAS community retaining their private data policy.

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Most of the data we use – images and data cubes – comes from NASA and ESA PDS/PSA data archives, exemplary vector datasets, e.g. global dune database from USGS and geological maps from PLANMAP-EU:

PDS data archives -- <https://pds.nasa.gov/>:

- MEX HRSC Reduced Data Records (REFDR)
- MRO CRISM Targeted Reduced Data Records (TRDR)
- MRO HiRISE
- MRO CTX (EDR)
- MGS MOLA
- LRO LROC

PLANMAP-EU -- <https://planmap.eu/>

- PLANMAP geological maps

USGS -- <https://www.usgs.gov/>

e.g.

- Mars Global Digital Dune Database MC–1
- Mars Global Digital Dune Database: MC2–MC29
- Mars Global Digital Dune Database: MC–30

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

The expected size of the data is about 100 TB.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Data, and the interfaces to explore the data, are meant to be used primarily by scientists, students and space engineers.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes. Linked to data products metadata regarding the processing steps carried out during their generation must be provided. Metadata can be provided either as an individual text file, as a text header section of the data file. For instance, GeoTIFF images allow keyword-value pairs of metadata in their headers, GeoPackage datasets will host any number of table, which can be used on metadata table(s).

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes. Planetary data will be available through OGC standards WCS, WMS, WFS, and the Catalogue Services for the Web (R1,R2), we may also use the Cascade service provided by GeoServer (R3) to proxy external services -- for instance, Rasdaman.

The IVOA registry is an important resource for data discovery, publishing our data through EPN-TAP -- specifically designed for Planetary data -- should effectively connect our data to the astronomical community.

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Dataset name conventions should simply replicate those from original data sources whenever original data or direct products from original data are provided. In case of direct products (e.g., recalibrated data), we must append an expression -- -NEANIAS -- to the dataset name as well as any metadata element (e.g., file header) that composes it.

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Data products by NEANIAS planetary services are dynamic in that they will be produced on users demand, according to individual use cases. Our services major goal is to abstract -- or ease -- the technical detail of well defined processes given well known data (sources). It is tough foreseen that the software providing the different products will evolve, or even different options for algorithms will be offered to the user. At this point, it is clear that a version should be assigned to the data products and that such version can be defined based on the software and the software version used.

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

To be defined.

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes.

2.1.15 Will you use standardized formats for some or all of your data?

Yes, for all of all data.

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes. All data formats – GeoTIFF, GeoPackage, PDS IMAGE – are open standards.

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes. Tools are many, and open, to access the data and services we provide.

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Accompanying the data product, whenever possible and convenient, it should be included metadata regarding the main processing steps carried out during the generation of it. Convenience and possibility of inclusion of such metadata depends on the file format data is to be stored; we don't want to provide multiple files to accomplish that (the metadata). For instance, GeoTIFF images allow basic keyword-value pairs, and GeoPackage allow the inclusion of table-formatted comments, free-format values.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No.

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

All planetary data used are public, the products are public as well.

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

As previously stated, the main interface for data access is through the employment of REST APIs (OGC and IVOA protocols), which means users will use proper software clients to request for data.

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

To be defined.

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

The decision of using standard protocols to access the data is supported by two aspects: a well-defined interface where a consistent set of uses cases is part of;

the availability or working implementations of clients (and servers).

Planetary geoscience -- as a spin-off, if I may, from Earth geoscience -- benefits from a mature, stable and wealthy software landscape where OGC standards are broadly used. In particular, providing access to NEANIAS Space/Planetary services, QGIS is a popular open-source GIS client software that will allow our users to access our data. As an extra feature, QGIS users can also access IVOA EPN-TAP services through the plugin developed during H2020 EPN-VESPA project.

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

To be defined.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

Yes.

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

The final data product will be released to the public as soon as the research studies related to the NEANIAS Space thematic services have been completed and the data have been prepared. There is no period of exclusive use by the data collectors.

Raw data will be maintained on internally accessible servers and made available on request at no charge to the user.

2.4.4 What internationally recognized license will you use for your data?

To be defined

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes. We will follow quality assurance procedures of the NEANIAS project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

We will provide metadata about the generation of data products, open source software and documentation as usual.

2.5 Allocation of resources

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?
To be defined.

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?
To be defined.

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?
To be defined.

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

We plan to secure the data of limited use with an authentication and authorization process.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No.

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

NEANIAS WP4 SPACE – Astrophysics Services – DMP

Template: Horizon 2020 External References

Data Repositories External Datasets Registries Services

Dataset Description

Data Repositories

GAIA Catalogues, VIALACTEA Knowledge Base, SKA Science Data Challenges

External Datasets

ATLASGAL Catalog, The Galactic Census of High and Medium-mass Protostars, MIPS GAL Catalog, WISE Catalog, Galactic Legacy Infrared Mid-Plane Survey Extraordinaire, Canadian Galactic Plane Survey, Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer, Southern Galactic Plane Survey, Co-Ordinated Radio 'N' Infrared Survey for High-mass star formation, 24 and 70 Micron Survey of the Inner Galactic Disk with MIPS, The VLA Galactic Plane Survey, Herschel infrared Galactic Plane Survey, VLA Sky Survey, James Clerk Maxwell Telescope, Three-mm Ultimate Mopra Milky Way Survey, H2O southern Galactic Plane Survey, The Multi-Array Galactic Plane Imaging Survey, GAIA Archive, Millimetre Astronomy Legacy Team 90GHz, SKA Science Data Challenge #1, BGPS Catalog

Registries

GAIA Registries, VLKB Registries

Services

GAIA Services, VLKB Services

The H2020 NEANIAS Project aims to design, deliver, and integrate into the European Open Science Cloud innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In particular the Work Package 4 is focused on the thematic services related to the Space environment. The Space environment comprises astrophysicists and planetary scientists that will handle data within three services: S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata service; S2- Map making and mosaicking for multidimensional images service; S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques service. This document describes datasets employed from astrophysics surveys mainly covering the Galactic Plane. Data holdings come partly from the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB) hosted at the Italian center for Astronomical Archives (IA2, hosted at INAF - Astronomical Observatory of Trieste) and partly from new data resources such as the GAIA Archive and SKA Data Challenges.

Dataset Description

1>Data Summary

1.1What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? The H2020 NEANIAS Project aims to design, deliver, and integrate into the European Open Science Cloud innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In particular the Work Package 4 is focused on the thematic services related to the Space environment. The Space environment comprises astrophysicists and planetary scientists that will handle data within three services: S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata service S2- Map making and mosaicking for multidimensional images service S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques service This DMP describes datasets collected in astrophysics surveys mainly covering the Galactic Plane. Data holdings come partly from the existing resources set up for the FP7 VIALACTEA project and are hosted at the Italian center for Astronomical Archives (IA2, hosted at INAF - Astronomical Observatory of Trieste) and partly from new data resources (such as the

D1.5 Data management plan, report aligned to the H2020 suggested template and FAIR principles

GAIA archive and SKA Data Challenges described below). The former VIALACTEA data resources were taken from public data collections and stored locally to fix some metadata annotations to let the added value services work properly. For this reason the links provided below might not provide exactly the same files/datasets as the one available through the VIALACTEA Knowledge Base (VLKB) services. A similar caveat might apply to some catalogues, like the WISE one, that, being too big, were filtered to fit the galactic plane as defined by the Hi-GAL survey (the starting point of the VIALACTEA project). Also, a few collections are not made available to non-authorized users since they have a different privacy policy (user authentication is in place to prevent access to them). GAIA data will be made available from the Data Processing Center of Turin (DPCT) in ALTEC (partner of NEANIAS WP4). The DPCT shall keep online the last two versions of the catalog so version 2 and 3 are available in RDBMS and files. Older catalog versions are available in as files. The last catalog release contains about 8 billion of sources reporting astrometric and spatial information. SKA Data Challenges data are provided by the Square Kilometre Array Organization (SKAO). So far we will employ the SKA Science Data Challenge #1 (SDC1) release consisting of images of simulated SKA continuum image in total intensity of the same field at 3 frequencies (560 MHz, representative of SKA Mid Band 1, 1.4 GHz, representative of SKA Mid Band 2 and 9.2 GHz, representative of SKA Mid Band 5) and 3 telescope integrations (8, 100, 1000 h as representative of a single, medium-depth and deep integration, respectively). Ancillary data consist of primary beams and synthesized beams for each frequency. A training set is also released, which consists in truth catalogues listing the objects in the simulated 1000 h data and their properties for a 5% of the field-of-view.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Most of the data consist of a set of heterogeneous collections of observational data, in form of 2D images or multi-dimensional radio cubes and catalogues mainly in Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) format. In particular the S1 and S2 services will consume a variety of surveys to analyze compact/extended sources and star formation regions within the Milky Way Galactic Plane in different wavelengths: InfraRed, Sub-millimetre continuum, Molecular and Atomic Line Surveys, Radio continuum, Molecular Masers available thanks to the VLKB. Each survey will retain its own data policy. Products of these analysis will be published in the major journals detailing the pipelines and workflows to obtain them and will be made publicly available within the space data services for further studies and analysis.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Most of the data came from public repositories, some of them will be released to the NEANIAS community retaining their private data policy.

What is the origin of the data?

In the following we list the archives of data employed for the three space services for the astrophysics community. More details can be found in the section related to the “External References”. FITS cubes came from the following radio cubes surveys and related archives: CHaMP, HOPS, ThrUMMS, JCMT-HARPS, MALT90, VGPS, GLIMPSE, CGPS, SGPS FITS images came from continuum surveys: CORNISH, MAGPIS, MIPS GAL, WISE, Hi-GAL, VLASS. Catalogues are mainly used in S3 services are from: WISE, ATLAS GAL, BGPS, MIPS GAL. The aforementioned data will be managed by the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB) service. The GAIA Archive will be employed in the S1 service involving a Virtual Reality application. Simulated data for SKA came from the data challenge and will be used for testing purposes in S3 service.

1.4 What is the expected size of the data?

The expected size of the data is about 6 TB

1.5 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The end-user communities mainly include astrophysics as well as computer scientists and software

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engineers interested in computer vision and machine learning. While service data and products may also have a high impact in space weather and mobile telecommunications.

2FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

FITS (Flexible Image Transport System), International Virtual Observatory Alliance Technical Specifications

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

not listed

Comment: We will use recommendations and standards of the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA).

2.1.4 URL/Description

2.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

2.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Comment: Each survey use its own file naming convention. For example Hlgal continuum generated images include in the file names reference to the galactic longitude and observation bandpass, ATLASGAL only the longitude reference (since it only involves one observation band), CHaMP cubes include a reference to the interest region label defined by the observing programme itself. In short, VLKB will provide a dataset identifier (DID) that will uniquely identify the dataset, keeping in the naming of that DID the survey label and the original file naming, so to make it unique within the VLKB. Uniqueness outside the VLKB will be ensured by a proper pre-pending identifier of the service/data collection, enforced through IVOA registration.

2.1.8 URL/Name

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Comment: The data will be updated following user requirements updates and novel analysis results (e.g. for compact/extended sources or filamentary structure detections) due to updates to the pipelines used to generate them. Versions of the data product that have been revised due to errors and any other updates (other than new data) will be retained in an archive system. A revision history document will describe the revisions made. Backups of the data files will be retained at the INAF IA2 data center.

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

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Comment: Yes, persistent identifiers in the form of dataset identifiers following the IVOA Identifiers specification will be used. These will be needed in the cutout/merging service and in general to point to the datasets in a consistent and unique way.

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

Persistent Unique Identifier

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

Comment: Following IVOA Recommendations whenever possible

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

OpenAIRE not listed

2.1.14 URL/Name

ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB)

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

Yes

2.1.16 Which standardised data formats do you plan on using?

Flexible Image Transport System

Comment: Yes, most of the data comes in FITS format or through VOTable formatted responses out of catalogue searches.

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

Comment: FITS files is an open standard in astrophysical data management and research since decades and all IVOA Recommendation are open in their definition, usage and governance. Transport of catalogued data can also use CSV format, which is open. FITS file format covers usages for images, data cubes, tabular information and other.

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

forsomedata

Comment: These datasets will be accessible from the NEANIAS Space services such as the ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) but also from other open source services such as Topcat since they will be exposed using the IVOA Table Access Protocol (TAP).

2.1.23 Please describe which data require proprietary tools to access the data?

None

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

Comment: No. This depends on the external data source that guarantee the quality of data.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

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some

2.2.3 Data type/ Reason/ URL

Each survey will retain its own data. Products of NEANIAS analysis using the three Space thematic services will be published in the major journals (possibly Open Access) detailing the pipelines and workflows to obtain them and will be made publicly available within the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB) for further studies and analysis.

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Not Listed

Comment: Data will be made available from the ViaLactea Knowledge Base service currently hosted at INAF IA2 center in Trieste (service deployed at: <http://ia2-vialactea.oats.inaf.it/>).

2.2.6 URL/Name

<http://ia2-vialactea.oats.inaf.it/> ViaLactea Knowledge Base

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

securewithbackupandrecovery

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

Yes

Comment: All VLKB data resources are deployed through custom or open protocol API that conform to IVOA Recommendations like TAP, SIAP, ConeSearch. To access them VO aware tooling may be needed, but the VLVA is built to provide all the functionalities needed to exploit these resource. The GAIA data is also available through VO standards, as well as a human browsable portal. SKA Data Challenges data are downloaded from the SKA telescope web portal.

2.2.9 Please provide links describing the methods for accessing the data.

VLKB methods to access data are described at the following link:

<http://vialactea.iaps.inaf.it/vialactea/eng/dbaccess.php> The available functionalities are: vlkb_search, vlkb_cutout and vlkb_merge. "vlkb_search" identifies what files' content overlap a region along a specific line of sight on the celestial sphere and described by a circle or a rectangular range around it. "vlkb_cutout" cuts the files on positional constraints and also on the velocity axis (if 3D cubes were investigated) to allow for efficient data transport on the net and work only on the relevant part of data. "vlkb_merge" merges adjacent files (from the same sub-survey, i.e. no information post-processing during the merge phase) into a single image/cube based on positional and velocity bounds.

<http://vialactea.iaps.inaf.it/vialactea/eng/dbaccess.php>

2.2.10 Please provide links describing the tools for accessing the data.

The ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) application (<http://vialactea.iaps.inaf.it/vialactea/eng/tools.4multi.php>) is the most user friendly tool to access VLKB data. Otherwise you can use TOPCAT (<http://www.star.bristol.ac.uk/~mbt/topcat/>) and its VO TAP query dialog.

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

publication

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Comment: Information on compact/extended sources and filamentary structures will be also made available.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

some

Comment: The data collections will be described using metadata information directly from the IVOA Observational Core Components Data Model specification. All the data and metadata annotation will be, wherever possible, aligned to IVOA standards and best practices, including vocabularies for concepts and units involved.

2.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes

Comment: As per the above 2.3.1 section, ontologies, vocabularies, controlled words listings and other semantic annotations will follow as much as possible the IVOA and IAU standards and definitions.

data?

your data? Yes

Increase data reuse

2.3.3 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

after

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of

Comment: We will follow quality assurance procedures of the NEANIAS project.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

uptofiveyears

2.4 Allocation of resources

2.4.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

useofinstitutioninfrastructure

Comment: FAIRness of data and services will be covered by INAF institutional resources (e.g. staff people and support service infrastructure) with funding coming also from existing or foreseen projects that will base their efforts on the same data and services here described. Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment: The NEANIAS WP4 Astrophysics Data Manager is Eva Sciacca and VLKB Data Manager is Marco Molinaro.

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutionalarchive

Comment: The data resources that fall within the VLKB will continue to be maintained as part of the

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INAF IA2 data center. Besides that, upgrades can happen on request by future projects, like it is happening currently with the ERC Synergy Grant ECOGAL and eventual future projects that will support maintenance and updates to the VLKB for research on star formation regions and galactic plane research. GAIA data will, of course be taken care by the ESAC center and is already mirrored in other data centers worldwide. SKA Data Challenges (current and future) data will be managed by the SKAO.

3Data Security

3.1What do you plan to do with research data of limited use

keptonsecure

Comment: We plan to secure the data of limited use with an authentication and authorization process.

4Other

4.1Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No